

China's anti-dumping investigation on pork imports from Europe: A retaliation in the making [Journal Article]

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Summary of output

This article explores Chinese economic retaliation through a case study of its anti-dumping investigation of EU pork, after the EU conducted an anti-subsidy investigation into Chinese-produced electric vehicles (EVs). China's probe aimed to sway key EU Council votes on EV tariffs, targeting Spain as the largest pork exporter—especially of offal, a difficult product to export elsewhere. Furthermore, China considered Spain particularly vulnerable to its influence because of promised Chinese investment into green tech sectors, including EV and battery factories. This case is instructive, as a continuation of China targeting the economic interests of EU Member States and pitting them against one another, with negative consequences for the EU's collective interest. The EU should build protective mechanisms against such actions and strengthen its unified approach to trade and investment.

Access to output

The journal article has been submitted to the The Journal of Geoeconomics and still pending, and is therefore not yet accessible on the DWARC – China Horizons' project website [[not yet published](#)] or on Bruegel's website [[not yet published](#)].